

Forest Fire Regeneration with Aromatic Plants

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Forest restoration with medicinal and aromatic plants after a forest fire in Galicia (NW Spain), as part of the LIFE-VAIA project

Increasing forest fire regeneration should take into account early, intermediate and late value chains derived from the forest restoration. Forest restoration is a very expensive activity that should be carried out carefully considering the products that can benefit the owners but at the same time the society. A forest stand can have different spatial and temporal forest revenues. From a temporal point of view, the capacity to develop an understory below the tree is strongly affected by the growth rate of the tree, from fast- to slow- tree rates, usually linked to the capacity of develop leaves and therefore canopy and also the capacity of light as a source of energy to reach the undercrops. Tree canopy cover developed use to be expanded in all tree species, but the canopy cover growth rate is different in the various tree species. This canopy cover should be considered when the agroecological biodiversity spatial use is considered, for example from grasses or highlight demanding crops/cereals in young stands to mushrooms in full canopy cover stand. Native Amazonian still uses the combination of woody perennials and herbaceous vegetation to increase the products obtained from the forest for medicinal, aromatic or culinary uses, that are combined with new crops like café or cacao. Knowledge about the more adequate combination that has been used in the past by EU farmers and foresters has mostly disappeared in the last century. Therefore new combinations have to be analysed to provide innovative tools to EU farmers that maximize the economic return.

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